

**ANALYZING WORD PARTS AND WORD CHUNKS, TYPES OF
ERRORS.**

Jakbarova Nasiba Pulatjonovna

A lecturer at Namangan State Institute of foreign languages named after
Is'hakkhan Ibrat

Rakhimova Muslima

A second year student at Namangan State Institute of foreign languages named
after Is'hakkhan Ibrat

Annotation: It is believed that the teaching word parts and word chunks is one of the most important parts of the traditional English teaching. It includes several essential features such as teaching word formation and word combination, a lexical approach, teaching lexical chunks, teaching word grammar, teaching phrasal verbs and teaching idioms. Every part of teaching these features consider different types of methods that focus on ability of students. This article aims to provide the information that analyzing word parts, affixation errors and how to teach students word parts and language chunks in easy way.

Keywords: Affixations, word forms, aspect, grammatical roles, categories, memorize, internal, phrase.

Introduction

Analyzing word parts and word chunks is a valuable skill that enhances vocabulary, aids in spelling and pronunciation, improves reading comprehension, and helps in error detection

Analyzing word parts and word chunks is important for several reasons:

1. **Understanding Word Meaning:** Breaking down words into smaller parts helps in understanding the meaning of unfamiliar words. By recognizing prefixes, suffixes, and root words, you can infer the meaning of the whole word.

2. Spelling and Pronunciation: Recognizing word parts helps in spelling and pronunciation. Understanding common prefixes and suffixes can help you spell words correctly and pronounce them accurately.

3. Vocabulary Expansion: Analyzing word parts can help expand your vocabulary. When you understand the meaning of common prefixes, suffixes, and root words, you can easily learn new words that share those components.

4. Error Detection: Analyzing word parts can help in identifying errors in spelling, grammar, and syntax. By breaking down words into chunks, you can spot mistakes more easily.

5. Improving Reading Comprehension: Recognizing word parts can aid in reading comprehension. It allows you to quickly grasp the meaning of complex words and sentences.

In English language we can see many principles of word formations and words can be created in different way. Firstly, affixations (by the addition of prefixes and suffixes) have an important role in forming words in this process. What is affixation actually? The affixation is an example of the result of adding affixes to the root fix. For example: less – effortless, ing – interesting, able – comfortable. There are four main types of affixes such as:

1. Prefixes
2. Suffixes
3. Infixes
4. Circumfixes

Many students may come across some difficulties with these affixes because they do not know exactly which affixes is the suitable one for the word. Meaning that, this is reason for mistakes in affixations.

The next thing that we should not forget to mention is that we also take into consider compounding, two or more words can join up to make one. For example: tooth+brush = toothbrush. Furthermore, we may create new words by conversion process, when a word in one context may serve as a noun and in another context may

be serve as a verb. These three steps (affixation, compounding, conversion) are the main methods of word formation process.

In next step we analyze some common errors types that students face in speaking and writing skills.

1. Affixation errors

English affixes are not to create new categories of words, but rather to illustrate aspects of grammatical roles of a word. Usually, affixes are used to show plural or singular of word, its tense, it is comparative or superlative and etc. The researchers could decide that there are only eight inflectional affixes in English language. They are as follows:

1. Past tense – ed
2. Past participle – en/ed
3. Third person singular – s/es
4. Progressive – ing
5. Comparative – er
6. Superlative – est
7. Plural – s/es
8. Possessive – ‘s

Moreover, (Ninsiana & Hakim, 2018) conducted a research on an analysis of inflectional affixes errors in argumentative writing. The first commonly error found was the use of –ed, the second one was the use of –s, and third one –es. It could be appeared that the students had difficulties in deciding to apply the correct affixes especially in tenses of the words.

2. Compounding errors

Another most common error type is compounding errors. In fact, compounding errors classified 8 categories. In English grammar compounding also called, composition, is when two or more words are added together to make a new word. For example the word timetable is a combination of the words time and table. Researches show that many students have also a problem with using compounding words

especially in writing. Because the meaning of compounding word may be more different when they added but many students do not realize it. As a result, it effects the whole meaning of the sentence.

3. Collocation errors

Next error type is collocation errors when words of collocation are not used together in a way that is natural for native speakers of a language. This may happen when a non-native speaker uses words in a combination inaccurately. Collocation errors can make communication uncertain or confusing, and it may impact on the overall fluency and accuracy language using of a person. Therefore we should take into consider collocations as a main part of the language.

The most common examples of collocation errors are:

“Do a mistake” – make a mistake

“Make a party” – have a party

“Give a call” – make a call

“Go to haircut” – get a haircut

We can say many error types that we use in English language however aforementioned mistakes are the most common of them.

Method and instruments

Language chunks.

One group of researchers analyze that how to help to the students by teaching chunks of language. The process is called “The access Approach”. It includes four main steps. The first one is “teaching”, the second one is “selecting”, the third one is “revealing” and the last one is “complement.

The ACCESS Approach

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“ The first is when they are told to memorize long lists of single words.

Second is when they realize just how many words there are to memorize and how long it will take.

The third is when they try to speak in the real world, and their memorized word lists do not help them communicate effectively.

There is a way to help your students: systematically teaching chunks of language.”

What is “chunk” actually?

Chunks are structures of words that are used together nearly in the same order. Phrasal verbs, fixed expressions, idioms, verb patterns and more can all be called ‘chunks’. “At the end of the day”, “by the way”, heavy rain” are examples of chunks.

It will be more efficient when students learn chunks as a phrase, because chunks have more than one word and it is a bit hard to remember them.

Conclusion

Learning to analyze word parts and word chunks can help avoid several problems:

1. **Misunderstanding:** By breaking down words into smaller components, you can better understand their meanings. This can prevent misunderstandings that may arise from misinterpreting unfamiliar or complex words.

2. **Spelling Errors:** Understanding common prefixes, suffixes, and root words can help improve spelling accuracy. When you know how word parts combine to form complete words, you are less likely to make spelling mistakes.

3. **Vocabulary Limitations:** Analyzing word parts can help expand your vocabulary. When you recognize common prefixes, suffixes, and roots, you can easily decipher the meanings of new words and incorporate them into your vocabulary.

4. **Reading Difficulties:** Recognizing word parts can aid in reading comprehension. It allows you to quickly grasp the meanings of unfamiliar words and sentences, making reading less challenging.

5. **Communication Issues:** When you understand word parts, you can express yourself more effectively. You can choose the right words and use them correctly, leading to clearer communication with others.

6. **Critical Thinking Skills:** Analyzing word parts encourages critical thinking skills. It requires you to break down words, infer meanings, and make connections between different words, enhancing your overall cognitive abilities.

Overall, learning to analyze word parts and word chunks can enhance language skills, prevent misunderstandings, improve communication, and boost overall literacy abilities.

In conclusion, in order to correct the errors in the using of words and their internal parts, students should divide the words into their integral parts (main part, affixes). Then they can choose the necessary addition depending on the meaning and grammatical structure of the word. Researches show that the main problem faced by students is not in the meaning of the words, but in the use of affixes in them.

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